

Effect of N, Zn and B Levels on Yield, N, Zn and B Concentration, Uptake and N Use Efficiency in Maize –Wheat Sequence in a Vertisol

P. S. Kulhare¹, G. T. Yedke¹, G. D. Sharma¹ and G. S. Tagore^{1*}

¹Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/IJPSS/2017/33135

Editor(s):

(1) R. Manikandan, Department of Plant Pathology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tamil Nadu, India.

Reviewers:

(1) Ibrahim Erdal, Süleyman Demirel University, Turkey.

(2) Kursat Korkmaz, Ordu University, Turkey.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19471>

Received 31st March 2017
Accepted 11th May 2017
Published 10th June 2017

Original Research Article

ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during 2010-12 at Research Farm of Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur (Madhya Pradesh) to study the effect of levels of N (0, 60, 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹), Zn (0, and 10 kg ha⁻¹) and B (0 and 1.0 kg ha⁻¹) on yield, N, Zn and B concentration, uptake and N use efficiency by maize and wheat in maize-wheat sequence in a Vertisol. The treatments of N were applied to maize and wheat crop. While the treatments of Zn and B were applied to only maize crop and their residual effect was observed in wheat crop. Application of increasing levels of N in maize and wheat significantly increased the yield, B concentration in grain and stover/straw and N, Zn and B uptake by maize and wheat over their respective control. The N application of 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ in wheat significantly increased the N, Zn and B concentration in grain and straw of wheat over control. The N use efficiency by maize and wheat significantly decreased with increasing levels of N.

The application of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B and its residual effect significantly increased the grain yield, N uptake, Zn and B concentration in grain and their uptake by maize and wheat, respectively over control. The B application of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ and its residual effect was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ for grain yield, B concentration in grain, N, Zn and B uptake by maize and wheat, respectively. The B application of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ significantly increased the N use efficiency by maize over control.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: gstagore@gmail.com;

Keywords: Uptake; N use efficiency; yield; wheat; zinc; boron;

1. INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is important product in the world for human and animal nutrition. Maize is important in agricultural economy as food for man and feed for animal including poultry. Nutrient management is one of the most important factors in crop production. The knowledge regarding the use of optimum dose of nutrients especially nitrogen, zinc and boron is of prime concern. The yield of a crop can be adversely affected by deficient or excessive supply of any one of the essential nutrients. However, in intensive agriculture nitrogen is the major nutrient which determining crop yield. Nitrogen plays an important role in plant growth as an essential constituent of cell components having direct effect on growth, yield and quality of crop. Nitrogen fertilization of maize influences dry matter yield by influencing leaf area index, leaf area duration and photosynthetic efficiency [1]. It is a fast growing exhaustive crop requires high amount of major nutrients (N and P) and micronutrient (Zn) to produce large biomass as its grain yield potential is twice as compared to other cereals crops [2]. The actual harvested yield of maize and wheat are low due to wide spread deficiency of N (89%) and Zn (49%) and in-sufficient pre plant N and lack of Zn application as maize and wheat are highly and mildly sensitive to Zn deficiency, respectively [3-4]. N is the most important growth element and it is most frequently deficient nutrient in most non legume cropping system. The response of maize to N and Zn application has been reported by [4-5], respectively.

Wheat is an important cereal crop, source of staple food and thus the most important crop in food security prospective. Besides its tremendous significance, average yield is far below than developed countries. Zinc has metabolically important role in plant growth and development and is therefore called an essential trace element or a micronutrient. It plays main role in synthesis of proteins, enzyme activation, oxidation and revival reactions and metabolism of carbohydrates. By utilizing of fertilizers contain zinc and other micronutrients, performance and quality of crops is gets enhanced and shortage of this elements due to decline in plant photosynthesis and destroys RNA, amount of soluble carbohydrates and synthesis of protein,

resulting in decrease in performance and quality of crop.

Zinc has a key role as a structural constituent or regulatory co-factor of a wide range of enzymes and proteins in many important biochemical pathways and these are mainly concerned with carbohydrate metabolism, both in photosynthesis and in the conversion of sugars to starch, protein metabolism, auxin (growth regulator) metabolism, pollen formation, maintenance of integrity of biological membranes and resistance to infection by certain pathogens. Zinc is an active element in biochemical processes and there is chemical and biological interaction between it and some other elements such as phosphorus, iron and nitrogen in plants.

Boron deficiency is a worldwide problem for field crop production where significant crop losses occur both in yield and quality. Availability of B to plants is affected by a variety of soil factors including soil pH, texture, moisture, temperature, oxide content, carbonate content, organic matter content and clay mineralogy Boron is generally less available in clay soils and availability increases with increasing temperature. Soil pH is regarded as a major factor regulating B availability in soils. Increasing pH favours its retention by soils or soil constituents. Thus, B fertilization is necessary for improvement of crop yield as well as nutritional quality.

After Zn, B is the second yield limiting micronutrient (33% deficient) which is essential for stimulating plant growth and in increasing yield of crops such as rice, wheat [6]. B and Zn deficiency upset the order of grains on the corn and make them deformed so that some parts of the corn ear are free from grain [7]. The information on interaction among N, Zn and B is hardly available in maize – wheat sequence in the region hence the investigation was undertaken.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted at Research Farm of Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur during 2010-12. The soils of the experimental site belongs to medium black clayey (Vertisol), pH 7.42, EC 0.16 dSm⁻¹, available N 164 kg ha⁻¹, P 33.6 kg ha⁻¹, K 200 kg ha⁻¹, DTPA extractable Zn 1.18 mg kg⁻¹ and hot water soluble B 0.49 mg kg⁻¹. The experiment

was conducted in a split plot design comprised of 4 levels of N (0, 60, 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹) as main treatments and 2 levels of Zn (0 and 10 kg ha⁻¹) and 2 level of B (0 and 1 kg ha⁻¹) as sub treatments were replicated thrice. N levels were applied in three split doses. 50% of N treatment, 35.2 kg P, and 33.2 kg K kg ha⁻¹ were applied as basal dose through urea, single super phosphate and muriate of potash, respectively in maize and wheat crop. Zinc and boron levels were applied to maize crop as basal dose and their residual effect was observed in wheat crop. Remaining 25 % N each was applied at knee height and silking stage of maize and crown root initiation and maximum tillering stage of wheat. The maize crop (JM 216) was sown on 9.7.2010 and 5.7.2011 @ 20 kg ha⁻¹ during first and second year respectively with spacing of 25 cm between plant to plant and 60 cm row to row. Two hand weeding were done on 10.08.2010 and 10.09.2010 during first year and 10.08.2011 and 10.9.2011 during second year. The maize crop was harvested on 16.10.2010 and 22.10.2011. The rainfall received 1451.2 mm and 1525.1 mm during growth period of maize during 2010 and 2011, respectively. The wheat crop (GW-273) was sown on @ 120 kg ha⁻¹ on dated 5.12.2010 and 23.11.2011 in the same field after the harvest of maize crop. Two hand weeding were done at 20 day interval after sowing of wheat crop. Four irrigations were applied to wheat crop at crown root initiation (CRI), tillering, flowering and seed formation stages of wheat. The wheat crop was harvested on 10.04.2011 and 7.04.2012. The plant samples of maize and wheat were collected at the time of harvesting for analysis of the nutrient concentration. The plant samples were washed with 0.1 N HCl and rinsed with distilled water and then dried at 60°C for 6 - 8 hours. The samples were grinded by stainless steel blade grinder and then used for chemical analysis. N concentration in grain and stover was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method as described by [8]. The plant Zn concentration was determined after digestion of plant sample with diacid mixture of nitric and perchloric acid in 2.5:1 ratio suggested by [9] using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Plant B concentration was determined by curcumin method as described by [10]. The nutrient uptake was calculated by multiplying the nutrient concentration X yield.

$$\text{N use efficiency} = \frac{\text{Increase in plant N uptake (kg ha}^{-1}\text{) due to N/Applied N level (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{X100}}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Maize Yield

The pooled data presented in Table 1 revealed that the increasing levels of N significantly increased the grain, stover and cob core yield of maize over control. However, the grain yield with 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but the difference between two N levels was found non-significant. While the stover and cob core yield successively and significantly increased with increasing levels of N. The increase of grain and stover yield of maize with increasing levels of N might be due to beneficial effect of N in vegetative growth, photosynthesis and in grain formation as N is a constituent of amino acid, protein and enzymes which are responsible for yield improvement. The increase of grain yield of maize with application of N was reported by [11-13].

The application of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1 kg B ha⁻¹ produced significantly higher grain yield. However, the grain, stover and cob core yield of maize with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn alone and combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The increase of grain, stover and cob core yield with Zn and B application might be due to beneficial effect of Zn and B on growth and yield of maize crop as Zn helps in enzyme activation, protection of bio membrane, hormone metabolism, nucleic acid, protein synthesis and seed formation. The interaction among N and Zn/B was found significant for grain and cob core yield of maize. The grain and cob core yield with the application of B of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn alone or combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ with all N levels. The maximum grain yield of 4.65 t ha⁻¹ was observed with 180 kg N + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ which was found significantly superior to lower levels of N. It might be due to synergistic effect of N and B application. The increase of grain yield with Zn application was reported by [14-18]. The promotive effect of B may be due to maintain membrane integrity, pollen tube development which affects seed setting and ultimately the crop yield. The increase of yield of maize with B and Zn fertilizers was reported by [19-21].

3.2 N Concentration and Uptake by Maize

The pooled data presented in Tables 1 and 2 revealed the application of N of 120 kg ha⁻¹

significantly increased the N concentration in grain and stover over control but the N level were found on par with higher or lower levels of N. The N uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total uptake significantly increased with increasing levels of N over control. However, the application of N of 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but the two N levels were found on par. The increase of N concentration in maize plant and its uptake with increasing levels of N might be due to increase of N availability in soil and which was taken up by plant. The increase of N concentration in and its uptake by maize with N application was confirmed by [22,13].

The application of 1.0 kg B alone and combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ were found significant over control for N concentration in stover. However, the 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ for N concentration in stover and N uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total N uptake by maize. The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant for N concentration in grain and its uptake. The combined application of 10 kg Zn+1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significant over 10 kg Zn and 1.0 kg B alone at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. While N concentration in stover with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significant over 10 kg Zn alone but it was found on par with combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The N uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total N uptake by maize with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn alone or combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ with 60, 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ except N uptake by grain and stover with combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. The N concentration in grain and its uptake by grain significantly increased with the application of Zn and B alone and combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The increase of N concentration in and its uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total N uptake by maize due to beneficial effect of Zn and B increasing the availability of N in soil. The increase of N concentration in and N uptake by maize due to Zn or B application was supported by [15,23,24].

3.3 N Use Efficiency by Maize

The data presented in Table 3 revealed that the application of N of 60,120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ resulted N recovery of 54.77, 48.20 and 35.31%

by maize crop, respectively which decreased significantly with increasing levels of N. This decreased N use efficiency might be due to increase of N losses with increasing levels of N and impropportionate increase of N uptake by maize. Similar results of N use efficiency in maize crop reported by [12].

The application of 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the N use efficiency over control and 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹. However, the N use efficiency with 1.0 kg B (59.74%) was found significantly higher than that at 10 kg Zn +1kg B ha⁻¹. The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant. The N use efficiency with the application of 1.0 kg B and conjoint use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 60 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to control or 10 kg Zn alone. The maximum N use efficiency 75.24 % was observed with 1.0 kg B + 60 kg N ha⁻¹ which decreased significantly with 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The increase of N use efficiency with B application might be due to beneficial effect of B application on increase of N uptake (Table 3). The increase of N use efficiency with B application was also reported by [22,20].

3.4 Zn Concentration and Uptake by Maize

The pooled data presented in Table 1 indicated that the maximum Zn concentration in stover 29.02 mg kg⁻¹ was observed in control but it significantly decreased with 60/120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The Zn concentration in stover with 60 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹ was found on par. The Zn uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total Zn uptake by maize significantly increased with increasing levels of N over control. However, the Zn uptake by grain successively and significantly increased with increasing levels of N. While the Zn uptake by stover, cob core and total Zn uptake by maize with 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ except Zn uptake by stover with 180 kg N ha⁻¹ but the difference between two treatment was found non-significant. The decrease of Zn concentration in plant with higher N levels might be due to dilution of Zn as a result of increased plant growth with higher N levels. The increased N uptake by maize with N application might be due to higher dry matter yield with N application. These results are in agreement with [12].

Table 1. Effect of N, Zn and B levels on yield and N, Zn and B concentration in maize (pooled data of 2010 and 2011)

Treatments	Main/Sub	Yield (tha ⁻¹)								N concentration (%)							
		N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD (P=0.05)	N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD (P=0.05)		
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	0.75	1.32	2.49	2.42	1.75	N levels	0.062	0.190	0.98	1.11	1.13	0.92	1.04	N levels	0.022	0.068
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	1.12	1.75	2.60	3.30	2.19	Zn/B	0.054	0.153	1.06	1.15	1.12	1.07	1.10	Zn/B	0.019	NS
	Zn ₀ B ₁	1.97	3.08	4.18	4.65	3.47	NXZn/B(1)*	0.107	0.305	1.04	1.15	1.10	1.05	1.09	NXZn/B(1)*	0.039	0.110
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	1.88	2.43	3.36	3.79	2.86	NXZn/B(2)**	0.142	0.403	0.83	1.15	1.24	1.07	1.07	NXZn/B(2)**	0.051	0.145
	Mean	1.43	2.15	3.16	3.54	2.57				0.98	1.14	1.15	1.03	1.07			
Stover	Zn ₀ B ₀	4.51	7.11	7.78	9.67	7.26	N levels	0.246	0.759	0.60	0.60	0.61	0.51	0.58	N levels	0.011	0.061
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	4.42	7.47	8.66	9.98	7.63	Zn/B	0.181	0.516	0.55	0.55	0.58	0.71	0.60	Zn/B	0.008	0.023
	Zn ₀ B ₁	5.10	7.95	9.60	10.12	8.19	NXZn/B(1)*	0.362	NS	0.66	0.75	0.77	0.77	0.74	NXZn/B(1)*	0.016	0.046
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	4.69	7.37	8.56	9.89	7.63	NXZn/B(2)**	0.529	NS	0.61	0.63	0.76	0.57	0.64	NXZn/B(2)**	0.023	0.066
	Mean	4.68	7.47	8.65	9.92	7.68				0.61	0.63	0.68	0.64	0.64			
Cob core	Zn ₀ B ₀	0.29	1.05	1.51	1.84	1.17	N levels	0.055	0.169	0.34	0.42	0.42	0.45	0.41	N levels	0.014	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	0.95	1.25	2.02	2.04	1.57	Zn/B	0.053	0.150	0.43	0.44	0.47	0.43	0.44	Zn/B	0.013	NS
	Zn ₀ B ₁	1.63	2.97	3.32	3.19	2.78	NXZn/B(1)*	0.106	0.301	0.46	0.40	0.47	0.45	0.45	NXZn/B(1)	0.027	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	0.97	2.39	2.29	2.89	2.14	NXZn/B(2)**	0.132	0.376	0.39	0.36	0.42	0.47	0.41	NXZn/B(2)	0.034	NS
	Mean	0.96	1.91	2.29	2.49	1.91				0.41	0.41	0.45	0.45	0.43			
		Zn concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)								B concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)							
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	24.79	26.64	30.19	29.44	27.76	N levels	0.922	NS	5.34	7.28	7.70	7.88	7.05	N levels	0.145	0.448
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	33.65	34.79	31.21	30.14	32.45	Zn/B	0.519	1.477	5.15	8.03	8.56	8.88	7.65	Zn/B	0.130	0.370
	Zn ₀ B ₁	30.93	29.26	25.91	30.28	29.10	NXZn/B(1)*	1.037	2.954	9.30	10.44	11.20	10.67	10.40	NXZn/B(1)*	0.260	0.737
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	34.57	36.41	33.88	30.64	33.87	NXZn/B(2)**	1.833	5.220	7.82	9.70	9.58	9.04	9.03	NXZn/B(2)**	0.338	0.958
	Mean	30.98	31.77	30.30	30.12					6.90	8.86	9.26	9.12	8.53			
Stover	Zn ₀ B ₀	25.92	20.08	21.48	20.07	21.88	N levels	0.596	1.838	10.71	14.98	15.82	16.44	14.49	N levels	0.378	1.166
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	26.84	28.83	32.80	22.93	27.85	Zn/B	0.549	1.562	11.95	15.16	15.73	18.15	15.25	Zn/B	0.336	0.957
	Zn ₀ B ₁	27.97	22.40	23.50	18.52	23.10	NXZn/B(1)*	1.097	3.125	13.98	14.32	15.39	17.57	15.32	NXZn/B(1)*	0.672	1.914
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	35.36	35.29	28.91	24.44	31.00	NXZn/B(2)**	1.403	3.997	16.04	18.00	17.00	13.36	16.10	NXZn/B(2)**	0.876	2.496
	Mean	29.02	26.65	26.67	21.49					13.17	15.62	15.99	16.38	15.29			
Cob core	Zn ₀ B ₀	23.25	23.53	19.85	26.24	23.22	N levels	0.538	NS	1.68	2.78	3.23	3.92	2.90	N levels	0.069	0.212
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	32.55	30.18	32.34	30.22	31.32	Zn/B	0.503	1.432	2.85	3.94	4.54	4.49	3.95	Zn/B	0.049	0.139
	Zn ₀ B ₁	26.39	28.41	27.95	27.44	27.55	NXZn/B(1)*	1.006	2.865	3.39	5.01	4.75	4.89	4.51	NXZn/B(1)*	0.098	0.278
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	32.19	30.94	31.65	28.97	30.94	NXZn/B(2)**	1.276	3.633	4.20	4.41	4.94	4.62	4.54	NXZn/B(2)**	0.146	0.416
	Mean	28.59	28.27	27.95	28.22					3.03	4.03	4.36	4.48	3.98			

* Comparison of two Zn/B levels at same level of N; **comparison of two N levels at same or different levels of Zn/B

Table 2. Effect of N, Zn and B levels on N and Zn uptake by maize (pooled data of 2010 and 2011)

Treatments	Main/Sub	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)								Zn Uptake (g ha ⁻¹)							
		N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)	N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)		
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	7.45	14.72	28.35	21.63	18.04	N levels	0.971	2.993	18.93	36.34	74.40	71.12	50.200	N levels	3.386	10.407
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	11.77	20.11	27.84	33.39	23.28	Zn/B	0.820	2.336	37.54	61.84	80.84	98.47	69.670	Zn/B	2.096	5.952
	Zn ₀ B ₁	20.37	35.37	45.94	48.67	37.59	NXZn/B(1)*	1.641	4.673	58.46	87.84	107.97	141.38	98.910	NXZn/B(1)*	4.191	11.901
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	16.31	27.87	41.90	40.13	31.55	NXZn/B(2)**	2.201	6.270	64.43	88.18	113.43	114.80	95.210	NXZn/B(2)**	6.896	19.583
	Mean	13.98	24.52	36.01	35.95					44.84	68.55	94.16	106.44				
Stover	Zn ₀ B ₀	27.07	42.01	46.64	47.36	40.77	N levels	1.992	6.141	132.96	157.13	183.48	217.37	172.730	N levels	7.102	21.830
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	24.14	40.27	48.43	71.18	46.00	Zn/B	1.481	4.217	125.27	226.11	305.81	249.66	226.710	Zn/B	6.933	19.688
	Zn ₀ B ₁	33.05	58.62	71.32	76.42	59.85	NXZn/B(1)*	2.961	8.434	168.43	192.04	243.36	202.43	201.560	NXZn/B(1)*	13.865	39.373
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	28.83	46.86	63.28	53.91	48.22	NXZn/B(2)**	2.961	8.434	180.45	287.58	259.66	263.27	247.740	NXZn/B(2)**	17.190	48.815
	Mean	28.27	46.99	57.42	62.22					151.77	215.72	248.08	233.18				
Cob core	Zn ₀ B ₀	0.99	4.67	7.22	9.07	5.49	N levels	0.526	1.621	6.74	25.40	26.80	46.20	26.300	N levels	1.853	5.712
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	4.13	5.73	10.20	8.98	7.26	Zn/B	0.380	1.080	31.20	39.00	65.40	59.40	48.800	Zn/B	1.900	5.400
	Zn ₀ B ₁	7.20	11.80	15.60	14.30	12.20	NXZn/B(1)*	0.760	2.160	40.90	83.20	92.60	87.50	76.000	NXZn/B(1)*	3.790	10.800
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	3.83	8.59	9.78	14.30	9.12	NXZn/B(2)**	1.120	3.200	29.70	74.20	72.80	82.60	64.800	NXZn/B(2)**	4.590	13.100
	Mean	4.04	7.70	10.70	11.70					27.20	55.50	64.40	68.90				
Total uptake	Zn ₀ B ₀	35.50	61.40	82.20	78.10	64.30	N levels	2.274	7.013	159.00	219.00	285.00	335.00	249.000	N levels	8.890	27.400
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	40.00	66.10	86.50	114.00	76.50	Zn/B	1.940	5.530	194.00	327.00	452.00	408.00	345.000	Zn/B	8.330	23.700
	Zn ₀ B ₁	60.60	106.00	133.00	139.00	110.00	NXZn/B(1)*	3.880	11.100	268.00	363.00	444.00	431.00	377.000	NXZn/B(1)*	16.700	47.400
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	49.00	83.30	115.00	108.00	88.90	NXZn/B(2)**	5.180	14.700	275.00	450.00	446.00	461.00	408.000	NXZn/B(2)**	21.100	60.100
	Mean	46.30	79.20	104.00	110.00					224.00	340.00	407.00	409.00				

* Comparison of two Zn/B levels at same level of N

**comparison of two N levels at same or different levels of Zn/B

Table 3. Effect of N, Zn and B levels on N use efficiency and B uptake by maize (pooled data of 2010 and 2011)

Treatments	Main/Sub	B uptake (g ha ⁻¹)								N use Efficiency (%)							
		N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)	Main/Sub	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)		
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	3.84	9.22	18.26	18.54	12.47	N levels	0.659	2.026	Zn ₀ B ₀	43.17	38.91	23.64	35.24	N levels	1.950	6.010
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	5.75	13.76	21.71	28.07	17.32	Zn/B	0.771	2.189	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	43.43	38.68	40.84	40.98	Zn/B	2.240	6.381
	Zn ₀ B ₁	19.23	32.80	47.14	49.72	37.22	NXZn/B(1)*	1.541	4.376	Zn ₀ B ₁	75.24	60.22	43.75	59.74	NXZn/B(1)*	4.480	12.760
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	15.02	23.50	31.66	33.75	25.98	NXZn/B(2)**	1.756	4.987	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	57.26	54.99	33.00	48.42	NXZn/B(2)**	5.145	14.654
	Mean	10.96	19.82	29.69	32.52	23.25				Mean	54.77	48.20	35.31				
Stover	Zn ₀ B ₀	46.10	108.08	126.27	164.33	111.20	N levels	5.174	15.904								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	49.73	113.78	138.72	191.41	123.41	Zn/B	3.466	9.843								
	Zn ₀ B ₁	70.56	109.45	141.45	183.50	126.24	NXZn/B(1)*	6.932	19.658								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	78.79	138.26	149.02	123.80	122.47	NXZn/B(2)**	10.787	30.632								
	Mean	61.30	117.39	138.87	165.76	120.83											
Cob core	Zn ₀ B ₀	0.49	2.90	4.94	7.16	3.87	N levels	0.295	0.910								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	2.71	4.87	9.30	9.06	6.48	Zn/B	0.240	0.700								
	Zn ₀ B ₁	5.61	14.90	15.70	15.60	13.00	NXZn/B(1)*	0.490	1.390								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	4.15	10.50	11.30	13.30	9.82	NXZn/B(2)**	0.660	1.890								
	Mean	3.24	8.30	10.30	11.30												
Total uptake	Zn ₀ B ₀	50.40	120.20	149.50	190.00	127.50	N levels	5.440	16.770								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	58.20	132.40	169.70	228.50	147.20	Zn/B	3.770	10.750								
	Zn ₀ B ₁	95.40	157.10	204.30	248.80	176.40	NXZn/B(1)*	7.550	21.500								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	98.00	172.30	192.00	170.80	158.30	NXZn/B(2)**	11.470	32.670								
	Mean	75.50	145.50	178.90	209.60												

* Comparison of two Zn/B levels at same level of N
 **comparison of two N levels at same or different levels of Zn/B

The application of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the Zn concentration in grain, stover, cob core and their Zn uptake over control except Zn concentration in stover with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. However, the Zn concentration in grain, stover and cob core with 10 kg Znha⁻¹ and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg Bha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ but the difference between the two treatment was found not significant for Zn concentration in grain and cob core. However, the Zn concentration in stover with combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone. It might be due to beneficial effect of Zn application in increasing the availability of Zn in soil and accumulated in plant and increased grain and stover yield of maize resulted higher Zn uptake. While the Zn uptake by grain and cob core with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ alone and combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone but the difference between the two treatment was found non-significant for Zn uptake by grain. Whereas the Zn uptake by stover and total Zn uptake by maize with combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was also found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn and 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ alone. The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant for Zn concentration and uptake. The application of 10 kg Znha⁻¹ alone and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ with 60 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹ were found significant over 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ for Zn concentration in grain, stover and cob core except Zn concentration in cob core at 60 kg N ha⁻¹. The maximum Zn concentration in grain 36.41 mg kg⁻¹ and stover 35.36 mg kg⁻¹ was observed with combined application of 10 kg Zn+ 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 60 and 0 N, respectively which decreased significantly with 180 kg N ha⁻¹. While the Zn uptake by grain with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ progressively and significantly increased with N levels over 10 kg Zn alone. While the combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ level was found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹. The Zn uptake by stover and total Zn uptake by maize was found significantly higher with 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 120 kg Nha⁻¹ than that of 1.0 kg B or combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B with lower or higher level of N. The significant increase of Zn concentration in and Zn uptake by maize with B and Zn fertilization was reported by [15,23-24].

3.5 B Concentration and Uptake by Maize

The pooled data presented in Table 1 revealed that the increasing levels of N significantly increased the B concentration in grain, stover and cob core over control but the treatments were found on par amongst themselves for B concentration in grain and stover. While the B concentration in cob core with 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly higher than that at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but the difference between the two level was found non-significant. However, B uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total B uptake by maize successively and significantly increased with increasing levels of N. An increase in B concentration in plant tissue as a result of B application is obviously due to enhanced availability of B in soil and subsequently its uptake by plant. These results are in agreement with the findings of [25]. The application of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn+1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the B concentration in grain and cob core as well as B uptake by grain, stover, cob core and total B uptake by maize over control but the treatments were found on par amongst themselves for B uptake by stover. However, the B concentration in grain and their uptake with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone and combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. Whereas the B concentration in stover was found significantly higher with combined application of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ than control. The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant for B concentration in grain, stover, cob core and their B uptake by maize. The B concentration in grain and cob core and their uptake with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at all N levels except B concentration in cob core with combined use of 10 kg Zn+1kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The B concentration in grain with 1.0 kg B +120 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 60 or 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The B concentration in stover was found significantly higher than 10 kg Zn and 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 60 kg N ha⁻¹. While it was found significant with 1.0 kg B+180 kg N ha⁻¹ than combined application of 10 kg Zn+1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The B uptake by grain with 1.0 kg B +120 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 1.0 kg B +60 kg N ha⁻¹ but it was found on par with 180 kg Nha⁻¹. The B uptake by stover and total B uptake by maize with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ alone successively and significantly

increased with increasing levels of N. The maximum B uptake by stover and total B uptake by maize was observed with 1 kg B + 180 kg N ha⁻¹ which was significantly higher than combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The application of Zn and B increased the B uptake by maize was reported by [26].

3.6 Wheat Yield

The pooled data presented in Table 4 revealed that the grain and straw yield significantly increased with increasing levels of N over control. However, the grain yield with N of 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but the difference between the two N level was found non significant. While the straw yield with 180 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly higher than that at 60 or 120 kg N ha⁻¹ but the N of 60 and 120 kg ha⁻¹ were found at par. The increase of grain and straw yield of wheat with increasing levels of N due to beneficial effect of N in better root growth higher N concentration and uptake. The increase of wheat yield with N application was reported by [27-28].

The residual effect of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the grain and straw yield of wheat over control but the treatments were found on par amongst themselves for straw yield of wheat. However, the grain yield with residual effect of 1.0 kg B was found significantly higher than that of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ but it was found on par with residual effect of combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1 kg B ha⁻¹. The increase of grain and straw yield of wheat due to beneficial effect of residual Zn and B in soil. The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant for grain and straw yield. The grain and straw yield with residual effect of B of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to the residual effect of combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. The treatment was also found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but it was found on par with higher levels of N. The increase of wheat yield due to residual effect of Zn was reported by [15,18,29-34] reported increase of yield of wheat with B application.

3.7 N Concentration and Uptake by Wheat

The pooled data presented in Table 4 and 5 revealed that the application of the increasing levels of N significantly increased the N

concentration in grain, straw and their N uptake and total N uptake by wheat over control except N concentration in grain with 60 kg N ha⁻¹. The N uptake by grain, straw and total N uptake by wheat followed the same trend. However, the N concentration in straw and N uptake by grain and straw and total N uptake with 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 60 kg N ha⁻¹ but the difference between the two treatment was found non significant. Consistently positive effect of N application on its concentration and uptake could be due to the increased availability of N in the soil with N application which resulted in greater absorption of N by plant due to better vegetative growth and root development. Similar results were recorded by [35,27].

The residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ and combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the N concentration in grain and straw, respectively over control but other treatments were found non significant over control. These treatments significantly increased the N uptake by grain, straw and total N uptake by wheat over control except N uptake by straw with 10 kg Zn alone. However, the N uptake by grain with residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to residual effect of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ alone. The interaction among N, Zn and B were found significant for total N uptake by wheat. The total N uptake by wheat with residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to residual effect of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ at 60 and 120 kg N ha⁻¹. The maximum N uptake 163.88 kg N ha⁻¹ was observed with residual effect of combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ which was also found significantly higher than that of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ at 60 kg N ha⁻¹. The increased N concentration in grain and straw of wheat with residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ and combined use of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B might be due to beneficial effect of Zn and B in increasing N availability in soil and resulted higher N concentration and uptake by wheat. These results are in agreement with [15].

3.8 N Use Efficiency by Wheat

The data presented in Table 5 indicated that the application of N of 60, 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ resulted N recovery of 69.69, 56.87 and 40.83 %, respectively which decreased significantly with increasing levels of N in wheat. The maximum recovery of N was observed at lower level of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ and minimum at higher level of N of 180 kg ha⁻¹. This decreased N use efficiency might be due to increased N losses and impropionate

increased N uptake by wheat with increasing levels of N as a result of decreased total dry matter production and competition among plant for N due to more available N in soil. The decrease of recovery efficiency of N in wheat with increasing levels of N was reported by [35].

The residual effect of B of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ significantly increased the N recovery over residual effect of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ but it was found on par with the residual effect of conjoint use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The increase of N use efficiency with B application might be due to beneficial effect of B application on increase of N uptake by wheat (Table 5). The interaction among N, Zn and B was found significant. The residual effect of B of 1.0 kg ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to residual effect of combined application of 10 kg Zn +1kg B at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ but it was found on par with 10 kg Zn alone. The N use efficiency with 1kg B +120 kg N ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to 180 kg N +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The increase of N use efficiency with B application was reported by [20].

3.9 Zn Concentration and Uptake by Wheat

The pooled data presented in Table 4 and 5 revealed that the application of N of 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ significantly increased the Zn concentration in grain and straw of wheat over control but the difference between the two N level was found non-significant. However, the Zn uptake by grain, straw and total Zn uptake of wheat progressively and significantly increased with increasing levels of N. The increase of Zn concentration and uptake by wheat might be due to beneficial effect of N application in increasing the Zn availability in soil due to decrease in pH. These results are supported by [36].

The residual effect of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the Zn concentration in grain, straw and their Zn uptake as well as total Zn uptake by wheat over control except Zn concentration in grain with 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. However, the Zn concentration in grain with residual effect of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to residual effect of 1 kg B ha⁻¹ but the two treatments were found on par.

While the residual effect of combined application of 10 kg Zn +1 kg B ha⁻¹ was also found significantly superior to residual effect of 1.0 kg B for Zn concentration in grain and straw and its Zn uptake and total Zn uptake by wheat but it was found on par with 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹. The increase of Zn concentration and uptake by wheat might be due to beneficial effect of residual Zn level in increasing the Zn availability in soil and resulted higher Zn uptake by wheat. The residual effect of Zn increased the Zn concentration and its uptake by wheat was also reported by [15,30-32].

3.10 B Concentration and Uptake by Wheat

The pooled data presented in Table 4 and 5 revealed that the increasing levels of N significantly increased the B concentration in grain and straw and their B uptake by wheat over control but the treatments were found on par amongst themselves for B concentration in grain and straw. However, the B uptake by grain, straw and total B uptake by wheat with N of 120 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ was found significantly superior to N of 60 kg ha⁻¹ but the difference between the two treatment was found non-significant. The significant increase of B uptake with application of N was reported by [32].

The residual effect of 10 kg Zn, 1.0 kg B and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ significantly increased the B concentration in and Zn uptake by grain and straw and total B uptake by wheat over control except B concentration in straw with 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹. However, the B concentration in grain and straw and its B uptake and total B uptake with residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ and combined use of 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ were found significantly superior to 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ except B concentration in straw with 10 kg Zn +1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The total B uptake by wheat with residual effect of 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ was also found significantly superior to the residual effect of combined application of 10 kg Zn + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹. The interaction between N and Zn/B was found significant for B concentration in grain and B uptake by straw. B concentration in grain and B uptake by straw with residual effect of 1.0 kg B was found significantly superior to residual effect of 10 kg Zn alone as well as Zn uptake by straw over combined use of 10 kg Zn +1kg B ha⁻¹ at 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹. The increase of B concentration and uptake with B application was reported by [34].

Table 4. Direct effect of N and residual effect of Zn and B levels on yield and N, Zn and B concentration in wheat (pooled data of 2010 and 2011)

Treatments	Main/Sub	Wheat yield (t ha ⁻¹)								N concentration (%)							
		N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD (P=0.05)	N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD (P=0.05)		
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	2.94	4.35	5.32	5.60	4.55	N levels	0.079	0.244	1.44	1.54	1.68	1.70	1.59	N levels	0.040	0.125
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	3.54	4.77	5.57	5.85	4.93	Zn/B	0.061	0.174	1.53	1.61	1.82	1.85	1.70	Zn/B	0.026	0.073
	Zn ₀ B ₁	3.66	5.25	5.90	5.85	5.16	NXZn/B(1)	0.122	0.348	1.59	1.67	1.84	1.83	1.73	NXZn/B(1)*	0.051	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	3.73	5.25	5.55	5.72	5.06	NXZn/B(2)**	0.173	0.493	1.51	1.65	1.80	1.71	1.67	NXZn/B(2)**	0.083	NS
	Mean	3.47	4.91	5.58	5.75					1.52	1.62	1.78	1.77	1.67			
Straw	Zn ₀ B ₀	4.36	6.67	7.53	8.66	6.81	N levels	0.196	0.604	0.42	0.56	0.59	0.60	0.54	N levels	0.011	0.034
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	5.24	7.43	7.85	8.52	7.26	Zn/B	0.111	0.315	0.47	0.57	0.59	0.63	0.56	Zn/B	0.012	0.034
	Zn ₀ B ₁	5.13	7.65	8.46	8.56	7.45	NXZn/B(1)*	0.221	0.630	0.51	0.57	0.66	0.66	0.60	NXZn/B(1)*	0.024	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	5.74	7.37	7.49	8.63	7.31	NXZn/B(2)**	0.390	1.110	0.47	0.59	0.60	0.63	0.58	NXZn/B(2)**	0.028	NS
	Mean	5.12	7.28	7.83	8.60					0.47	0.57	0.61	0.63	0.57			
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	23.87	25.32	25.90	26.72	25.45	Zn concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)			8.36	14.94	15.02	13.71	13.01	B concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)		
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	27.31	28.21	28.35	27.78	27.91	N levels	0.465	1.324	10.74	15.33	15.71	15.98	14.44	N levels	0.410	1.265
	Zn ₀ B ₁	24.74	26.05	25.72	26.91	25.86	Zn/B	0.388	1.106	14.40	16.17	17.99	18.31	16.72	Zn/B	0.337	0.959
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	26.91	28.21	28.74	30.10	28.49	NXZn/B(1)*	0.777	NS	15.72	17.47	17.68	17.78	17.16	NXZn/B(1)*	0.673	1.918
	Mean	25.71	26.94	27.17	27.88		NXZn/B(2)**	1.049	NS	12.31	15.98	16.60	16.44		NXZn/B(2)**	0.919	2.618
Straw	Zn ₀ B ₀	8.14	8.35	8.58	9.24	8.58	N levels	0.264	0.814	5.38	6.84	7.81	7.44	6.87	N levels	0.305	0.941
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	9.39	9.74	10.23	10.53	9.97	Zn/B	0.183	0.521	5.78	8.07	8.11	7.83	7.44	Zn/B	0.267	0.760
	Zn ₀ B ₁	8.95	9.24	9.39	10.46	9.51	NXZn/B(1)*	0.366	NS	7.98	9.34	10.25	9.60	9.29	NXZn/B(1)*	0.533	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	9.18	9.86	11.28	11.28	10.40	NXZn/B(2)**	0.556	NS	6.89	9.14	8.70	7.84	8.14	NXZn/B(2)**	0.702	NS
	Mean	8.91	9.30	9.87	10.38					6.51	8.35	8.72	8.18				

* Comparison of two Zn/B levels at same level of N
 **comparison of two N levels at same or different levels of Zn/B

Table 5. Direct effect of N and residual effect of Zn and B levels on NUE and N, Zn and B uptake by wheat (pooled data of 2010 and 2011)

Treatments	Main/Sub	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)								Zn uptake (g ha ⁻¹)							
		N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)	N ₀	N ₆₀	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	SEm±	CD(P=0.05)		
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	42.68	67.08	89.79	95.10	73.75	N levels	3.143	9.692	69.76	109.74	137.76	149.72	116.75	N levels	2.470	7.592
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	53.64	76.89	101.50	109.60	85.17	Zn/B	1.624	4.695	95.32	134.04	157.55	162.01	137.23	Zn/B	2.644	7.508
	Zn ₀ B ₁	57.78	87.25	108.40	107.00	90.11	NXZn/B(1)*	3.248	NS	89.30	136.35	151.13	156.87	133.41	NXZn/B(1)*	5.287	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	56.56	87.58	100.50	98.18	85.72	NXZn/B(2)**	6.129	NS	98.00	147.49	159.14	172.14	144.19	NXZn/B(2)**	6.266	NS
	Mean	52.66	79.71	100.03	102.40					88.10	131.90	151.39	160.18	132.89			
Straw	Zn ₀ B ₀	22.13	38.41	44.70	48.69	38.48	N levels	1.318	4.063	35.89	55.62	64.52	79.71	58.94	N levels	1.732	5.324
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	28.80	42.29	45.80	49.92	41.70	Zn/B	1.141	3.249	49.15	72.25	80.37	89.81	72.89	Zn/B	1.663	4.722
	Zn ₀ B ₁	28.81	42.29	55.50	53.91	45.13	NXZn/B(1)*	2.293	NS	45.78	70.21	79.34	87.28	70.65	NXZn/B(1)*	3.327	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	28.17	44.04	45.42	50.58	42.06	NXZn/B(2)**	3.040	NS	52.68	72.73	84.61	95.96	76.50	NXZn/B(2)**	4.159	NS
	Mean	26.98	41.76	47.86	50.78	41.85				45.88	67.70	77.21	88.19	69.74			
Total	Zn ₀ B ₀	64.81	105.49	134.50	143.79	112.14	N levels	3.840	11.838	105.66	165.36	202.28	229.43	175.68	N levels	2.834	8.071
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	82.44	119.18	147.26	159.27	127.04	Zn/B	1.753	4.993	144.47	206.28	237.92	251.82	210.12	Zn/B	3.128	8.910
	Zn ₀ B ₁	86.59	129.59	163.88	160.89	135.24	NXZn/B(1)*	3.506	9.985	135.08	206.56	230.47	244.15	204.06	NXZn/B(1)*	6.256	NS
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	84.75	131.62	145.92	148.76	127.76	NXZn/B(2)**	7.331	20.820	150.68	220.22	243.75	268.10	220.69	NXZn/B(2)**	7.311	NS
	Mean	79.65	121.47	147.89	153.18					133.97	199.61	228.60	248.38	202.64			
Grain	Zn ₀ B ₀	24.12	65.43	80.03	77.58	61.79	N levels	2.858	8.785	Zn ₀ B ₀	67.80	58.08	43.88	56.59	N levels	2.651	8.174
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	37.64	73.15	87.19	93.70	72.92	Zn/B	2.058	5.844	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	61.18	54.02	42.58	52.59	Zn/B	2.258	6.430
	Zn ₀ B ₁	52.23	84.45	106.59	107.01	87.57	NXZn/B(1)*	4.115	NS	Zn ₀ B ₁	71.67	64.41	41.28	59.12	NXZn/B(1)*	4.515	12.860
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	58.98	91.65	97.89	101.78	87.57	NXZn/B(2)**	6.100	NS	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	78.12	50.98	35.57	54.89	NXZn/B(2)**	6.031	17.180
	Mean	43.24	78.67	92.92	95.02					Mean	69.69	56.87	40.83	55.80			
Straw	Zn ₀ B ₀	24.01	44.83	58.87	64.43	48.03	N levels	2.410	7.408								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	30.58	59.59	63.70	66.67	55.13	Zn/B	1.641	4.660								
	Zn ₀ B ₁	39.74	71.45	87.25	82.91	70.34	NXZn/B(1)*	3.283	9.323								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	39.14	67.32	64.91	68.20	59.89	NXZn/B(2)**	5.050	14.341								
	Mean	33.37	60.79	68.68	70.55												
Total	Zn ₀ B ₀	48.13	110.26	138.89	142.01	109.82	N levels	3.991	12.268								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₀	68.22	132.73	150.88	160.37	128.05	Zn/B	2.988	8.485								
	Zn ₀ B ₁	91.97	155.89	193.84	189.92	157.91	NXZn/B(1)*	5.975	NS								
	Zn ₁₀ B ₁	98.11	158.97	162.80	169.98	147.46	NXZn/B(2)**	8.635	NS								
	Mean	76.61	139.46	161.60	165.57												

* Comparison of two Zn/B levels at same level of N
 **comparison of two N levels at same or different levels of Zn/B

4. CONCLUSIONS

The application of 120 kg N + 1.0 kg B ha⁻¹ produced the maximum grain yield (4.18 t ha⁻¹) of maize and addition of 120 N ha⁻¹ alone in wheat gave the maximum grain yield of wheat (5.9 t ha⁻¹) in maize-wheat sequence. The maximum N and B concentration in grain and their uptake and recovery efficiency of N was observed with 1.0 kg B+120 kg N ha⁻¹ in maize-wheat sequence.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors of the manuscript are highly thankful to JNKVV, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh and AICRP on MSN (ICAR) for providing facility to carry out the research on this aspect.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Siam SH, Abd-El- Kader, GM, El-Alia IH. Yield and yield components of maize as affected by different sources and application rates of nitrogen fertilizer. *Research Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences*. 2008;4(5):399-412.
2. Tollenaar M, Lee E. Yield potential, yield stability and stress tolerance in maize. *Field Crops Research*. 2002;75:161-169.
3. Sharma PD. Nutrient management-challenges and options. *Journal of Indian Society of Soil Science*. 2008;55(4):395-403.
4. Havlin JH, Tisdale SL, Beaton JD, Nelson WL. *Soil fertility and Fertilizers: An introduction to nutrient management*, 7th Eds Dorlings Kindersley (India) Pvt, Ltd.; 2007.
5. Cakmak I. Enrichment of cereal grains with zinc. *Agronomic or genetic bio-fortification. Plant and Soil*. 2010;302:1-17.
6. Sakal R, Singh AP, Sinha RB. Evaluation of rate and frequency of B application in cropping systems. *Fertilizer News*. 2002; 10:37-38.
7. Marschner H. *Mineral nutrition to higher plants*. Acad. Press. London. 1995;301-306.
8. Piper CS. *Soil and plant analysis*. Hans Publisher, Bombay; 1950.
9. Jackson ML. *Soil chemical analysis*. Prentice hall of India Pvt Ltd.; 1973.
10. Black CA. *Method of plant and soil analysis*. (Part 2). American Soc. Agronomy, Inc. Publication Medicon, Wisconsin, USA; 1965.
11. Sharar MS, Ayub M, Nadeem MA, Ahmad N. Effect of different rates of N, P on growth and grain yield of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Asian Journal of Plant Science*. 2003; 2:347-349.
12. Nemati AR, Sharifi RS. Effect of rates and nitrogen application timing on yield, agronomic characteristics and nitrogen use efficiency in corn. *International Journal of Agriculture and Crop Science*. 2012; 4:534-539. Available:<http://pakacademicsearch.com/pdf-files/agr/70/534-539.pdf>
13. Rawal R, Kuligod VB. Influence of graded doses of nitrogen on nutrient uptake and grain yield of maize (*Zea mays*) under varying levels of soil salinity. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Science*. 2014; 27:22-24.
14. Alam MS, Islam N, Jahiruddin M. Effect of Zn and B application on the performances of local and hybrid maize. *Bangladesh Journal Soil Science*. 2000;26:95-101.
15. Adiloglu A, Adiloglu S. The effect of B application on the growth and nutrient concentration of maize in Zn deficient soils. *Research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Science*. 2006;2:1-4.
16. Hossain MA, Jahiruddin, Khatim F. Response of maize varieties to Zn fertilization. *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research*. 2011;36:434-447.
17. Badiyala D, Chopra P. Effect of Zn and FYM on productivity and nutrient availability in maize (*Zea mays*)- linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) cropping sequence. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 2011;56: 88-91.
18. Faujdar RS, Sharma M. Effect of FYM, biofertilizers and Zn on yield of maize and their residual effect on wheat. *Journal of Soil and Crops*. 2013;23(1):41-52.
19. Sahrawat KL, Wani SP, Murthy VS. Diagnosis of secondary and micronutrients deficiencies and their management in rain-fed. *Soil Science and Plant Analysis*. 2010; 41:346-360.
20. Shukla AK. Micronutrient research in India: Current status and future strategies. *Journal of Indian Society of Soil Science*. 2011;59:S-88-98.
21. Sarkar AK. Micronutrient management in soils for higher crop productivity. *Journal of*

- Indian Society of Soil Science. 2011;59: S58-66.
22. Wang DQ, Guo PC, Cheng GH. The fertilizer response of crops to urea containing borate. Journal of Shandong Agricultural University. 1992;23(2):108-113.
23. Potarzycki J, Grzebisz W. Effect of zinc foliar application on grain yield of maize and its yielding components. Plants Soil Environment. 2009;55:519-527.
24. Aref F. The effect of boron and Zinc application on concentration and uptake of N, P and K in corn grain. Indian Journal of Science and Technology. 2011;4:785-791. Available:<http://www.indjst.org/index.php/indjst/article/viewFile/30111/26062>
25. Sentimentla Singh AK, Singh S. Response of soybean to P and B fertilization in acidic upland soils of Nagaland. Journal of Indian Society of Soil Science. 2012;60:167-170.
26. Stalin P, Singh MV, Muthumanickam D, Chitdeshwari T, Velu V, Appavu K. Four decades of research on management of micro and secondary nutrients and pollutants elements in crops and soils of Tamil Nadu. Research Bulletin. 2010;1-105.
27. Rahman MA, Sarkar MA, Z Amin MF, Jahan AHS, Akhter MM. Yield response and nitrogen use efficiency of wheat under different doses and split application of nitrogen fertilizer. Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research. 2011;36:231-240.
28. Rahimi A. Effect of potassium and nitrogen on yield and yield components of dry land wheat in Boyerahmad Region of Iran. Annals of Biology Research. 2012;3:3274-3277.
29. Chaube AK, Ruhella R, Chakraborty R, Gangwar MS, Srivastava PC, Singh SK. Management of Zn fertilizers under Pearl millet-wheat cropping system in a Typic Ustipsamment. Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science. 2007;55:196-202.
30. Prasad RK, Kumar V, Prasad B, Singh AP. Long term effect of crop residues and Zn fertilizers on crop yield, nutrient uptake and fertility buildup under rice-wheat cropping system in Calciorthents. Journal of Indian Society of Soil Science. 2010;58:205-21.
31. Rathore DD, Meena MC, Patel KP. Evaluation of different Zn-enriched organics as source of Zn under wheat-maize (fodder) cropping sequence on Zn deficient Typic Haplusterts. Journal of Indian Society of Soil Science. 2012; 60:50-55.
32. Kulhare PS, Choudary MK, Uike Y, Sharma GD, Thakur RK. Direct and residual effect of Zn alone and incubated with cow dung on growth characters, Zn concentration, uptake and quality of soybean (*Glycine max (L) Merril*)-wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) in a Vertisol. Soybean Research. 2014;12(2).
33. Soylu S, Topal S, Sade B, Akgun N, Gezgin S, Babaoglu M. Yield and yield attributes of durum wheat genotype as affected by B application in B-deficient calcareous soils. Journal of Plant Nutrition. 2004;27:1077-1106.
34. Khan R, Gurmani AR, Khan MS, Jalal UD, Gurmani AH. Residual, direct and cumulative effect of boron application on wheat and rice yield under rice-wheat system. Sarhad Journal of Agriculture. 2011;27.
35. Yadav BL, Vyas KK. Influence of sub-surface compaction on recovery and use efficiency of N in wheat crop on highly permeable soils. Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science. 2006;54:158-162.
36. Zou BJ, Portch S. Effect of the micronutrients B and Zn on crop nutrient balance. Proceedings of the Int. Symp. on role of S, Mg and micronutrients in plant nutrition. 1992;344-351.

© 2017 Kulhare et al.; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciedomain.org/review-history/19471>